

OpenAIRE Demonstrator

MSCR

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Abstract Among its many efforts, the OpenAIRE Graph metadata aggregation team is dedicated to enhancing the interoperability and quality of metadata across diverse research repositories. One significant effort in this direction is defining crosswalks between metadata standards and the OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repositories v4 metadata schema so as to facilitate the implementation of OpenAIRE guidelines by repositories adopting such standards. Specifically, this document reports on the demonstration activities performed by the OpenAIRE Graph metadata curation team in using the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry Service (MSCR), developed under the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, to define and share crosswalks from known standards (e.g. Dublin Core, Datacite, CERIF), widely adopted and supported by many scholarly institutional repositories, and the OpenAIRE Guidelines. OpenAIRE Graph metadata curators, as well as any other provider of SKGs or aggregators, could benefit from the adoption of the MSCR as part of the aggregation methodologies, by involving data source managers as an actor of the process. Crosswalks from data source standard (or proprietary) formats to other formats could this way be collaboratively maintained by data source managers, SKG and aggregator providers, and the community as a whole, ensuring up-to-date expert-defined mappings are transparently maintained. This document describes the effort and issues identified while using the TRL7 MSCR service to accomplish this task, with the aim of identifying issues, limits, and requirements for the service.

Description relevant to Zenodo The FAIRCORE4EOSC (FC4E) project foresees in a number of demonstrators, eg. planning and implementing operational environments which can show the added value of (one of) the FC4E components and provide the FC4E development teams with additional requirements.

One of the components being worked on in the project is the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR), which should make the management of metadata schema and crosswalks more

easy for researchers and operational teams that need to execute bulk conversions of metadata records obeying different schema. In the FC4E project already two such cases are considered, managing the schema and crosswalks for the B2FIND and B2SHARE services.

The OpenAIRE team considers and discussed that the MSCR can also provide such management services for the OpenAIRE Graph Aggregation process by the OpenAIRE Graph curation team, defining crosswalks between metadata standards and the OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repositories v4 metadata schema.

Overall the aim is to contribute to the MSCR design and development, by identifying the requirements that OpenAIRE's use case brings into the picture and reporting the gaps and the limits of the current implementation. The new requirements will be discussed and prioritized during the last year of the FC4E project, M24-M36

This work took place in the context of FC4E Task 4.5 by OpenAIRE staff.

Introduction

The OpenAIRE Graph aggregates data from a vast array of repositories that employ various metadata schemas, including Dublin Core. This diversity introduces several challenges, primarily related to normalizing Dublin Core metadata (and its different dialects) to an internal OpenAIRE Graph schema that enables effective internal processing and robust data analytics. To handle this normalization, OpenAIRE relies on transformation scripts that convert heterogeneous metadata schemas into a unified schema and format, as defined by the OpenAIRE Guidelines¹.

However, the heterogeneous nature of metadata schemas and customized modifications introduced by individual repositories necessitate the definition and maintenance of numerous transformation scripts. This approach presents significant scalability challenges for the OpenAIRE aggregation team. Each new data source registration often demands the understanding and creation of a unique transformation script, i.e. a "crosswalk", which may be subject to updates and often requires feedback from the repository providers.

To partially mitigate these issues, OpenAIRE has developed and introduced its own metadata schema: the OpenAIRE Guidelines, with the latest iteration being version 4 (v4). OpenAIRE mandates repository (aka data source) managers to adapt these guidelines to streamline the aggregation process and ensure seamless integration within the OpenAIRE infrastructure. On the other hand, repository managers must cope with the implementation of mappings from their internal metadata formats to the OpenAIRE guidelines. Some repository platforms provide such exports out-of-the-box as part of the software modules, but in many cases, the crosswalk must be implemented from scratch. The challenge is not in software development but rather in defining the correct crosswalks, from schema to schema, from vocabulary to vocabulary, from format to format, reflecting corresponding structure and semantics.

The Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR) provides a solution to facilitate this transition. By utilizing the MSCR, communities that create a crosswalk between their data source's metadata schema and the OpenAIRE Guidelines v4 can openly share it with others for them to reuse. Such crosswalks serve as a comprehensive guide, facilitating other data source providers to map their metadata schemas onto OpenAIRE's (and EOSC's) schemas. Ultimately, this alignment supports the

¹ <http://guidelines.openaire.eu>

broader goals of enhancing metadata quality, ensuring interoperability via EOSC Interoperability Frameworks, and promoting the principles of Open Science.

Specifically, this document reports on the effort of using the MSCR to define and share a crosswalk between Dublin Core metadata schema to the OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repositories v4 metadata schema. The aim is to contribute to the MSCR design and development, by identifying the requirements that OpenAIRE's use case brings into the picture and reporting the gaps and the limits of the current implementation.

Figure 1: Flow of data from data sources to OpenAIRE

Use-case: OpenAIRE Graph and aggregation of data sources

The OpenAIRE Graph can aggregate metadata records from various kinds of data sources, including literature repositories, data repositories, and CRIS systems. To ensure their metadata records are compliant with OpenAIRE Guidelines v4, data source managers can utilize the comprehensive documentation available at [OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repository Managers](#). The guidelines (i) recommend the usage of OAI-PMH, FTP, or REST API (paged) protocols; and (ii) highlight mandatory, recommended, and optional metadata attributes, provide detailed vocabulary and format specifications, and include examples of correct implementation (e.g., [title field documentation](#)). Data source managers can validate the quality of their metadata exports using the OpenAIRE Validator tool, part of the [OpenAIRE PROVIDE](#) service capabilities. The Validator automatically interacts with a data source via the APIs provided by managers, computes a measure of the compatibility level of their metadata with OpenAIRE standards, and identifies any anomalies that need addressing. When the validation test is positive, the data source manager can register the data source to the OpenAIRE Graph and request its aggregation. Below is a screenshot of OpenAIRE PROVIDE illustrating validation results:

Figure 2: Output of validation process of a data source which was performed in OpenAIRE PROVIDE

Challenges

Depending on the technologies underlying their data source, data source managers can follow different methodologies to achieve OpenAIRE guidelines compliance. Customers of ePrints, DSpace, and DataVerse platforms can count on software modules that can be installed to ensure compliance with OpenAIRE Guidelines. Still, to some extent, such modules need to be fine-tuned to ensure format-to-format and vocabulary-to-vocabulary compliance. In the case of proprietary installations, data source managers need to make sure their metadata protocol and export format comply with the specifications of the OpenAIRE Guidelines. In both scenarios, defining the perfect mapping is not straightforward. For example, a correct mapping of resource types (e.g. articles, preprints, data, software, workflow) onto the [COAR Vocabulary of Resource Type](#) is essential to ensure metadata records in the data source are correctly classified in the OpenAIRE Graph and in the EOSC, guaranteeing proper research assessment and reporting to the Commission can be performed. The OpenAIRE Graph partially supports this process:

- The [OpenAIRE PROVIDE](#) service can help data source managers refine their crosswalks, as its capabilities harvest the records from the data source and return compliance reports, pointing out issues in protocol implementation (for OAI-PMH), malformed records, unmatching vocabulary terms, and values mismatching the expected formats. However, this is not enough to ensure that crosswalks maximize the amount of information that can reach the Graph (indeed, the less information is mapped the more the chances are to be compliant);
- The OpenAIRE Graph applies a light-weight harmonization process, with crosswalks that capture the exceptions and fix them before the records enter the Graph: for example resource types that are not properly mapped onto the COAR Vocabulary, author names that do not match the “Surname, Name” structure, etc. However, this is not enough to ensure optimal crosswalks, as any information loss takes place at the original data source and cannot be restored by the OpenAIRE aggregation process.

In summary, as of today, this picture suffers from two main drawbacks:

1. Data source managers cannot learn from other similar crosswalk experiences: their crosswalks are hidden in their implementation and only managers have control over them;

- The OpenAIRE Graph aggregation applies fixes that are (i) hard to maintain in the long term, as they are data source dependent (the Graph has defined more than 2400 data sources) and (ii) potentially misaligned with the perspective of the data source managers, experts of the local publishing workflows.

Requirements

In order to address the aforementioned drawbacks, and ensure an optimal and simplified aggregation process, the following capabilities would be required:

- Data source managers should be in charge of the crosswalks, but these should be shared for other data source managers to re-use or refine (when same schemas and interpretations are adopted);
- The OpenAIRE Graph (as well as any SKGs) should rely on crosswalks defined by data source managers, to ensure adherence to community requirements and transparency (provenance).

MSCR in support of the OpenAIRE Graph use-case

By design, the MSCR service could and should serve both these requirements and purposes, as it supports the co-creation, sharing, and access of crosswalks. In the following, we report the outcome of the experimentations we have performed using MSCR service (<https://mscr-test.rahtiapp.fi>) to create and share metadata formats and crosswalks between them, using as target the OpenAIRE Guidelines v4.

Registration of schemas

We registered the following formats, common in the OpenAIRE data source settings: DataCite, Dublin Core, CERIF, and the OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repositories 4.0.

OpenAIRE demo	Datacite	XSD	datacite-v4.xsd
OpenAIRE demo	Dublin Core	XSD	https://www.dublincore.org/schemas/xmls/simpledc20021212.xsd
OpenAIRE demo	Common European Research Information Format (CERIF)	XSD	openaire-cerif-profile.xsd
OpenAIRE demo	OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repositories v4	XSD	openaire.xsd

Schema upload and registration went smoothly, with one exception: CERIF. This schema features circular references, which the current MSCR version cannot handle. As of May 2024, the issue is under fixing and should be addressed in the next service release.

Creation of a crosswalk

Creating a crosswalk with the MSCR requires the selection of a source and target schema and the editing of a list of field-to-field mappings.

We started with Data Cite to OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature repositories 4.0 and everything went smoothly, as the latter is a DataCite application profile.

We have tested the definition of a crosswalk from Dublin Core to OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature repositories 4.0 and things got interesting. The fields “creator” and “contributor” in Dublin Core can

have a template structure, such as “Manghi, Paolo” and could therefore find an appropriate mapping onto the “creatorName”, “familyName”, “givenName” subfields in the OpenAIRE schema.

The screenshot shows a mapping tool interface with two panels. The left panel is titled "Dublin Core" and shows a search from source schema. The right panel is titled "OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repositories v4" and shows a search from target schema. A central button with a link icon is positioned between the two panels.

Dublin Core - Selected node info:

- @id: msc:root/Root/creator
- title: creator
- @type: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string>
- type: string

OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repositories v4 - Selected node info:

- @id: msc:root/Root/creators/Creator/creator/Creator/creatorName
- title: creatorName
- @type: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string>
- type: string

The MSCR does not allow for the inclusion/upload of actual mapping functions, as this would be bound to a specific implementation or programming language, but allows users to write a textual descriptions of the expected behavior of the mapping. The specification of a one-to-many fields mapping is addressed via multiple mappings between the field of origin (creator) and the many target fields (givenName, etc.).

Add mapping

The screenshot shows the "Add mapping" dialog. On the left, the source field is "creator" (Type: string, Description: N/A). On the right, the target field is "familyName" (Type: string, Description: N/A). A central "Predicate" dropdown menu is open, showing options: Exact match, Broad match, Broader, Broader transitive, Close match, Exact match (checked), Narrow match, and Narrower.

Mappings	
Source	Target
creator	familyName
Mapping type: http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#narrower	Notes: Write a function that, depending on the name template used by the origin data source, extracts the surname from it
creator	creatorName
contributor	creatorName
rights	rights

Feedback to designers and developers

In the following we report a list of suggestions/recommendations that could be taken into account in the future developments of the service.

Crosswalk editor UIs

We have found the design of the editing UI very reasonable, here are some nice-to-have features:

Information about field semantics During the definition of the mappings it would be important for the user to visualize information about the semantics of the individual fields: this could be provided via URL or via integration with DTR service;

Meaning of mapping types The list of types of mappings (e.g. “exact match”) requires a deeper explanation, as it is not always intuitive;

One-to-many mappings As highlighted above, “one field to many fields mappings” are expressed as a list of field-to-field mappings. For visualization purposes, it would be handy to have field-to-field mappings grouped by origin field (e.g. see the case of “creator” in the picture above); as in some cases they appear sparse over a long list.

Vocabulary maps The service could (and should) allow users to associate a field-to-field mapping than involves a source and target vocabulary with a function that specifies the terms-to-term (many to one) map between the two; ideally, users should be able to manage such a map from the crosswalk editing UI, although the map could be an object on its own, to be shared (or co-edited) with other users. Deep integration with the DTR service and/or SKOS systems could be a solution.

Crosswalks management

In managing the crosswalks, the following capabilities could be useful to improve exploitation:

Supplementary material Users to upload and share any material that could become handy to third-party willing to implement a given crosswalk: software libraries in GitHub, XSLTs, test data, documentation, etc.;

Crosswalk download Users to download a CSV version of the mapping, or a PDF in a documentation style of the mapping;

Co-editing Users to co-design a mapping, by delegation or by request to edit (Google Drive-like);

Notifications Consumers of the crosswalks are also implementers of the crosswalks in their own applications and would certainly wish to be notified of any changes that may occur, so as to reflect the change in their code;

Crosswalks as EOSC research products MSCR to become a data source of crosswalks, to be interpreted as research products in the EOSC Knowledge Graph; users should become “authors” of the crosswalk, for scientific attribution reasons.

Crosswalk data model

The OpenAIRE Graph features hundreds of data sources that export metadata records complying with a given schema (e.g. DataCite) but different interpretations of such schemas, e.g. vocabularies, value templates, value types. In practice, using the MSCR to manage crosswalks from DataCite to OpenAIRE Guidelines would require defining multiple crosswalks that reflect exactly the same field-to-field structural mapping but different mapping semantics, specified via textual notes.

Decoupling structural and semantic mappings A possible solution could be to have a crosswalk as a combination of a structural mapping and an *interpretation*” of such mapping, which could be specific to a given data source. In this scenario, data source managers would select a structural crosswalk and define their own associated interpretation.